

Stress of Yoga doer and Yoga non Doer Teachers

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the current study is to look into the stress levels and mental health of school teachers who practice yoga and those who don't. A sample of 120 school teachers, 30 of whom were male teachers and 30 of whom were female teachers, were included in the research, representing both yoga practitioners and non-practitioners. The mental health inventory was given to each participant, and the results of the stress inventory were examined using the 't' test. The findings showed that there is a noteworthy disparity in mental health between male and female yoga instructors who practice yoga and those who do not. When compared to school teachers who do not practice yoga, yoga practitioners have better mental health. Regarding their stress score, a significant difference is also seen between school teachers who practice yoga and those who do not.

INTRODUCTION

One significant aspect of our lives that adds a lot of stress is our work or jobs. Because work-related stress negatively affects employees' emotional and physical well-being and has a substantial financial impact on the company, it is a growing source of concern.

Teachers' stress: Teachers' stress can become problematic and even harmful when they believe that their needs are not being met or that their perceived ability to handle the challenges they face is being exceeded.

Causes of Teachers Stress- Teachers stress can be caused by number of factors both external and internal. External cause may include institutional conditions such as large mixed ability classes, lack of resources, overwork distribution of workloads, poor communication, unclear expectations and inadequate rewards and recognition (Brown and Ralph, 1998).

Problematic relationships with students can lead to other pressures, such as personality conflicts, a lack of community spirit, a sense of isolation, a lack of support, and restricted possibilities for social and intellectual engagement with other instructors. Internal factors could be a competitive, irritable, or aggressive personality. Particularly unrealistic self-expectations and a negative attitude towards students are traits of the personality.

Impact of Teachers' Stress: Educators who experience stress often exhibit behaviors such as poor time management, difficulty focusing, job dissatisfaction, aggression and irritability, introversion, and withdrawal from supportive relationships. Emotional repercussions include feelings of worry, unhappiness, and resentment; depression; an inability to unwind and relax; a low sense of self-worth; and, finally, burnout; long-term physical effects include exhaustion and low energy; irregular sleep patterns; eating disorders; and possibly psychosomatic illnesses and heart diseases. Health is a condition of complete mental, physical, and social well-being. We refer to our whole psychological well-being as mental health. It includes how we see ourselves, the quality of our relationships with others, and our ability to manage our emotions and get beyond challenges. There is more to being mentally well than simply not experiencing any mental health problems. Those who are mentally or emotionally healthy have control over their emotions and actions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The primary goal of the current study was to compare the stress and mental health of school teachers who practice yoga with those who do not. The following are some of the main goals that were established in order to investigate the issue:

1. To investigate the mental health of male school teachers who practice yoga and those who do not.
2. To investigate the mental health of female school teachers who practice yoga and those who do not.
3. To investigate stress in male school teachers who practice yoga and those who do not.
4. To investigate stress in female school teachers who practice yoga and those who do not.

METHODOLOGY

Sample selection

There were 120 teachers in the sample, both male and female, who practiced yoga and those who did not. The sample was chosen from Aurangabad city using accessible sampling approaches and purposeful sampling. Out of the 120 teachers, 30 were yoga practitioners and 30 were not, and 60 of them were female (30 yoga practitioners and 30 non-practitioners). Regarding age, marital status, and other factors, all of the teachers were matched.

Tools

Occupational stress index developed by Sing and shrivastava was used.

Variables under Study:

1. Independent variable: Teachers
2. Dependent variable: Stress

Proposed Statistical Procedure:

1. Descriptive statistics i.e. Mean, S.D, will be computed.
2. 't' test

RESEARCH RESULT

Table 1: Displaying the t-value of the stress level in male instructors who practice yoga and those who don't.

Older Adults	No.	Mean	SP	t value	sig
Yoga doer	30	69.07	13.11	2.23	0.05
Yoga non-doer	30	76.89	14.02		

Table 2: Displaying the findings of the "t" value of stress in female instructors who practice yoga and those who don't.

Older adults	No.	Mean	SP	t value	Sig
Yoga doer	30	70.11	13.20	2.01	0.05
Yoga non-doer	30	77.36	14.86		

The study's conclusions are based on the comments of 120 instructors – 60 of whom practice yoga and 60 of whom do not – about their experiences with professional stress. Table 1 shows a substantial difference between the comparative groups' mean stress scores (M=69.07 for group 1 and M=76.89 for group 2). Because the "t" value (2.23) is significant at 0.05 levels, the "t" test thus indicated a statistically significant difference in the stress level of male teachers who practice yoga and those who do not. In contrast to male yoga instructors, it is evident that male participants who are not practitioners experience higher levels of stress.

Table 2's results show that the stress scores of the two comparison groups differ significantly. Table 4 made it abundantly evident that compared to yoga

practitioners, female yoga non-teachers' mean stress levels (M=77.36) were higher.

DISCUSSION

1. When it comes to their occupational stress, yoga practitioners and non-practicers would differ significantly.
2. When it comes to their level of occupational stress, school teachers in rural and urban areas would differ significantly.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The primary goal of the current study was to compare the stress levels of male and female yoga instructors who practiced and those who did not. The following result was reached following study and interpretation.

1. The guy who practiced yoga was less stressed than the guy who didn't.
2. Compared to female yoga non-participants, the female yoga practitioner exhibited lower stress levels.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

They can overcome obstacles in life, forge enduring bonds with others, and bounce back from failures. When we are in a condition of good mental health, we are able to recognize our own strengths, manage the typical stressors of life, and go to work on a regular basis. Yoga is a useful tool for maintaining physical and mental well-being.

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